

**CLINICO COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF SRAMSANA
PROPERTY OF MESHASHRUNGI PHALA (GYMNEMA SYLVESTRE
R.BR.)- A RANDOMISED STUDY**

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ABSTRACT

Background: *Sramsana karma* one among *Virechana karma*, is the Method of expelling the adhered *Pakva* (formed stool) and *Apakva Koshtagata* (partially formed stool) *Maladi*. *Maladi* includes vikruta Dosha and Purisha. *Acharya Charaka* explains *Sramsana karma* eradicates *Pitta* and *Pittashaya Kapha* and *Pitta*. **Objectives:** To evaluate *Sramsana property* of *Meshashringi Phala*(*Gymnema sylvestre R.Br.*) clinically and to compare *Sramsana property* of *Meshashringi Phala*(*Gymnema sylvestre R.Br.*) with standard *Aragwadha*(*Cassia fistula Linn.*) *Phala majja* clinically. **Methodology:** 30 volunteers were selected and assigned into 2 groups and *Aragwadha Phalamajja churna* and *Meshashringi phala churna* was given to each group respectively and *Sramsana Karma* was observed. **Result:** The *Meshashringi Phala*(*Gymnema sylvestre R.Br.*) acts as *Sramsana* as it expelled both *Pakwa* and *Apakwa Koshtagata Mala*. It is observed that the parameters viz. total number of *Vegas* and

Dravata of the stool was more in the volunteers of Group II (*Meshashringi phala churna*) compared with Group I(*Aragwadha phala majja churna*). Whereas other parameters viz.

latency period, duration of *Virechana* and *Antiki lakshana* were almost similar in both the groups. **Discussion:** The *Ushna virya* and *Katu vipaka* of *Meshashringi Phala* and anthraquinone fistulic acid present in the fruit is contributed for purgation. **Conclusion:** As per classics of Ayurveda, the *Aragwadha phalamajja* is the *Shreshtha Dravya* for *Sramsana karma* but as mentioned in *Bhavaprakasha nighantu* and *Kayadeva nighantu*, the present study confirms the *Sramsana karma* of *Meshashringi phala* clinically. Both *Meshashringi phala* and *Aragwadha phala majja* act as *Sramsana* so *Meshashringi phala* can be used in place of *Aragwadha phala majja* for *Sramsanakarma*.

KEYWORDS: *Meshashringi phala*, *Aragwadha phala majja*, *Sramsana karma*, anthraquinone fistulic acid.

INTRODUCTION

Sramsana karma^[1] one among *Virechana karma*, is the Method of expelling the adhered *Pakva* (formed stool) and *Apakva Koshtagata* (partially formed stool) *Maladi*. *Maladi* includes vikruta Dosha and Purisha. *Acharya Charaka*^[2] Explains *Sramsana karma* eradicates *Pitta* and, *Pittashay Kapha* and *Pitta*.

Bhavaprakasha^[3] and *Kaiyadevanighantukara*^[4] explains the *Sramsana* as one of the *Karma* of *Meshashringi Phala*. *Acharya Sushruta*^[5] enumerates its *Twak* has *Shirovirechana karma*.

Meshashringi (*Gymnema sylvestre* R.Br.)^[6] belongs to *Asclepiadaceae* family is a Large woody much branched climber; Leaves :3.2-5 by 1.3- 3.2 cm., ovate, elliptic, or ovatelanceolate, acute or shortly acuminate, more or less pubescent on both sides, sometimes densely so beneath, base rounded or cordate, sometimes cuneate. Inflorescence: pedunculate or nearly sessile cymes; Fruits: Follicles terete, rigid, lanceolate, attenuated into a beak, glabrous, one follicle often suppressed. Fruiting usually during January to March. Seeds 1.3 cm. long, narrowly ovoid-oblong, flat, with a thin broad marginal wing, brown, glabrous.

Both *Bhavaprakasha Nighantu* and *Kaideva Nighantu* explains properties of *Meshashringi* (*Gymnema sylvestre*R.Br.) *Phala* as *Tikta rasa yukta*, *Vatala*, *Kaphahara*, *Dipana*, *Sramsana*, useful in *Kushtha*, *Meha*, *Kasa*, *Krumi*, *Vrana* and *Visha*.

Meshashringi (*Gymnema sylvestre*R.Br.) known as *Madhunashini* locally is very popular for its anti diabetic use both in traditional and folk lore medicine. It is easily distributed in westem ghats and other places. So easily available and cost effective. *Acharya*

Sharangadhara^[1] mentions *Aragvadha* (*Cassia fistula* Linn.) as *Shreshtha Dravya* for *Sramsana* and its a tradition to use same for *Sramsana*. Here an attempt will be made to search another efficient *Dravya* for *Sramsana karma*. So that during non availability of *Aragvadha*(*Cassia fistula* Linn.), one can use easily available *Meshashringi* (*Gymnema sylvestre*R.Br.) *Phala* for *Sramsana karma*.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

OBJECTIVES

1. To evaluate *Sramsana* property of *Meshashringi Phala*{*Gymnema sylvestre* R..Br.) clinically.
2. To compare *Sramsana* property of *Meshashringi Phala*(*Gymnema sylvestre*R.Br.) with standard *Aragvadha*(*Cassia fistula* Linn.) *Phala majja* clinically.

HYPOTHESIS

H0: There is no difference in *Sramsana karma* of *Meshashringi Phala*(*Gymnema sylvestre*R. Br.) and *Aragvadha* (*Cassia fistula* Linn.) *Phala majja*.

H1: There is a difference in *Sramsana karma* of *Meshashringi Phala* (*Gymnema sylvestre*R.Br.) and *Aragvadha* (*Cassia fistula* Linn.) *Phala maiia*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Type of study: Clinical study

The study was undertaken after obtaining Institutional Ethical clearance IEC No. SGV/AMC/329/2024-25.

Source of data: Healthy volunteers satisfying with *Madhyama Koshta* was selected from Hostel of SGV Ayurvedic Medical and hospital research Center Bailhongal Karnataka. Informed consent was collected from participants. Informed consent was taken from each volunteer.

Koshta of the volunteers was assessed based on following criteria:

Table No. 01: Assessment criteria of Koshta.

Sl.no.	Domain	Criteria	Grade
1	Frequency of stool	2 times a day	0
		Once a day	1
		Passing stool on alternate days	2
2	Consistency of stool	Unformed	0
		Formed	1

		Formed and hard	2
3	Quantity of stool	Bahu	0
		Normal	1
		Alpa	2
4	Passing of stool(usually)	Without any effort and satisfactory	0
		With normal efforts and unsatisfactory	1
		With more efforts and unsatisfactory	2
5	Usually time taken for defecation	1-5 min	0
		5-10min	1
		More than 10 min	2
6	Feeling of urge for defecation	Feeling of urge upon waking up in the morning	0
		Feeling of urge within 10-30 min of waking up	1
		Not feeling of urge and needs to consume food	2
7	Effect of taking hot milk, hot water, etc	Watery loose stool and frequent	0
		Slightly loose but formed stool once	1
		No effect	2

Sample size: 30, selected volunteers were randomly assigned in to 2 groups.

Group A: was given *Aragvadha (Cassia fistula Linn.) Phala majja*

Group B: was given *Meshashringi Phala(Gymnema sylvestreR.Br.) churna*.

Collection of study drug: Study Drug was collected from *Dhanwantri vana* of SGV Ayurvedic Medical college and was authenticated by HOD of Dravyaguna vignana, SGV AMC Bailhongal.

Preparation of drug: *Meshashringi Phala(Gymnema sylvestreR.Br.)* was made into *Sukshma churna* as per SOP mentioned in API in Rasashastra and Bhaishajya kalpana Department of SGV AMC Bailhongal.

Route of administration: Oral.

Method of administration: Each patient from group A was given 12-24gm^[8] of *Aragvadha(Cassia fistula Linn.) Phala majja churna* and Each patient from group B was given 12-24gm of *Meshashringi Phala(Gymnema sylvestreR.Br.)churna* on empty stomach with hot water respectively.

After administration of the medicine volunteers were kept under observation in vaccumm free environment. Total no of *Vegas*, Latency period, Duration of *Virechana*, *Antiki lakshana* and consistency of stool was observed in both the groups thoroughly and noted down.

Consistency of stool was assessed based on Bristol stool scale.

Table no. 02: Showing Bristol stool scale.

Type	Form of stool
1	Separate hard lumps, like nuts (hard to pass)
2	Sausage -shaped, but lumpy
3	Like a sausage but with cracks on its surface
4	Like a sausage or snake, smooth and soft
5	Soft blobs with clear cut edge (passed easily)
6	Fluffy pieces with ragged edges, a mushy stool
7	Watery', no solid pieces, entirely liquid

- Types 1 and 2 indicate constipation.
- Types 3 and 4 being the ideal stools (especially the latter), as they are easy to defecate without containing any excess liquid.
- Types 5,6,7 are tending towards diarrhea.

The obtained Data was subjected to statistical analysis in SPSS version 25 software.

OBSERVATIONS

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

Group I: *Aragwadha (Cassia fistula Linn)*^[7]: Gender wise distribution showed that 53.33% were female and the rest male. The total number of *Vegas* for the 15 participants are detailed in table 05. The latency period (time taken to produce first motion after taking the drug) is detailed in table 06. The duration (taken between onset of first *Vega* and *last Vega*) of *Virechana* is detailed in table 07. Majority of volunteers showed *Malantha* 60%, *Kaphanta* 6.66%, *Pittanta* 33.33%, Consistency of passed stools during each *Vega* was assessed using Bristol stool scale and is showed in table 09.

Group II: (*Meshashrungi (Gymnema sylvestreR.Br.)*^[7]: Gender wise distribution showed that 53.33% were female and the rest male. The total number of *Vegas* for the 15 participants are detailed in table 05. The latency period (time taken to produce first motion after taking the drug) is detailed in table 06. The duration (taken between onset of first *Vega* and last *Vega*) of *Virechana* is detailed in table 07. Majority of volunteers showed *Malantha* 53.33%, *Kaphanta* 20%, *Pittanta* 26.66%, Consistency of passed stools during each *Vega* was assessed using Bristol stool scale and is showed in table 10.

Table No. 03: Showing Age wise distributions of Volunteers.

AGE	Group I	Percentage	Group II	Percentage
18-19	2	13.33%	1	6.66%
20-21	4	26.66%	3	20%
22-23	7	46.66%	7	46.66%
24-25	2	13.33%	4	26.66%

Graph No. 01.

Table No. 04: Showing Sex wise distribution of volunteers.

Sex	No. of Volunteers			
	Group I	Percentage	Group II	Percentage
Male	7	46.66%	5	33.33%
Female	8	53.33%	10	66.66%

Graph No. 02.

RESULTS

Group I (*Aragwadha*(*Cassia fistula* Linn.))^[7]: Number of stools produced by single dose of 12 -24 g was considered as total number of *Vegas*. The Mean number of *Vega* was 9.067. The Mean latency of *Aragwadha* (*Cassia fistula* Linn.) was 229.333. It ranged from 180-370

minutes. The mean duration of *Sramsana* in volunteers of group I was 152.667. It ranged from 70- 245 minutes. In this group *Aragwadha*(*Cassia fistula* Linn.) produced *Malantha* in 60% volunteers, *Kaphanta* in 6.66% volunteers, *Pittanta* 33.33%. Consistency of the stool produced by the volunteers was observed based on Bristol stool scale and their total number was recorded. In this group *Aragwadha*(*Cassia fistula* Linn.) produced Type-6 (40%) and Type-7 (60%) stools in the volunteers.

Group II(*Meshashrunji*(*Gymnema sylvestre*R.Br.))^[7]: Number of stools produced by single dose of 12 -24 g was considered as total number of Vegas. The Mean number of *Vega* was 12.667. The Mean latency of *Meshashrunji*(*Gymnema sylvestre*R.Br.) was 271.4. It ranged from 168-370 minutes. The mean duration of *Sramsana* in volunteers of group II was 161.667. It ranged from 70-242 minutes. In this group *Meshashrunji*(*Gymnema sylvestre*R.Br.) produced *Malantha* in 53.33% volunteers, *Kaphanta* in 20% volunteers, *Pittanta* 26.66%. Consistency of the stool produced by the volunteers was observed based on Bristol stool scale and their total number was recorded. In this group *Meshashrunji*(*Gymnema sylvestre*R.Br.) produced Type-6 (40%) and Type-7 (60%) stools in the volunteers.

Statistical Analysis

In the present study number of *Vegas*, latency periods and duration of *Virechana* when compared in both groups found to be non-significant. Whereas the consistency of stool assessed by Bristol stool scale found to be significant (Type 7).

Total number of *Vega* observed in each group is tabulated as follows: GROUP I & II

Table No. 05: Showing the Total number of vegas.

Volunter No	No of Vegas- Group 1 <i>Aragwadha</i> (<i>Cassia fistula</i> Linn.)	No of Vegas – Group 2 <i>Meshashrunji</i> (<i>Gymnema sylvestre</i> R.Br.)
1	16	26
2	5	4
3	5	6
4	10	5
5	6	7
6	9	10
7	6	15
8	6	20
9	6	12
10	9	22
11	6	21

12	10	9
13	5	7
14	21	16
15	16	10

Note: Total number of *Vegas* were calculated by leaving first two *Mala Vegas*.^[7]

Graph no. 03.

Latency period of volunteers (in min) observed in each group is tabulated as follows:

Table No. 06: Showing the Latency period (in)min.

Volunter no	Group 1- <i>Aragwadha</i> (<i>Cassia fistula</i> Linn.)	Group 2 – <i>Meshashrungi</i> (<i>Gymnema sylvestre</i> R.Br.)
1	190	168
2	270	370
3	185	310
4	190	180
5	370	220
6	260	230
7	250	260
8	240	168
9	180	320
10	190	300
11	230	350
12	260	355
13	185	310
14	240	360
15	200	170

Note: Time of administration of drug and time of initiation of first *Vega* were noted. Latency was calculated by subtracting time of onset of first *Vega* from the time of administration of drug.

Graph No. 04.

Duration of *Virechana* (in min) observed in each group is tabulated as follows

Table No. 07: Showing the Duration of *Virechana* (in min).

Volunter no	Group 1- Aragwadha (Cassia fistula Linn.)	Group 2 –Meshashrungi (Gymnema sylvestreR.Br.)
1	200	242
2	120	60
3	240	120
4	80	210
5	70	70
6	130	190
7	140	100
8	90	198
9	210	160
10	200	140
11	190	190
12	100	195
13	125	150
14	150	200
15	245	200

Note : Time of last *Vega* was noted and duration of *Virechana* was calculated by subtracting the time of last *Vega* from the time of onset of *Vega*.^[7]

Graph No: 05.

Lakshana observed in each group is tabulated as follows

Table No. 08: Showing the *Antiki Lakshana*.

Volunter No	Group 1- <i>Aragwadha</i> (<i>Cassia fistula</i> Linn.)	Group 2 – <i>Meshashrungi</i> (<i>Gymnema sylvestre</i> R.Br.)
1	<i>Malanta</i>	<i>Malanta</i>
2	<i>Malanta</i>	<i>Malanta</i>
3	<i>Malanta</i>	<i>Malanta</i>
4	<i>Malanta</i>	<i>Pittanta</i>
5	<i>Malanta</i>	<i>Pittanta</i>
6	<i>Malanta</i>	<i>Pittanta</i>
7	<i>Malanta</i>	<i>Malanta</i>
8	<i>Pittanta</i>	<i>Kaphanta</i>
9	<i>Malanta</i>	<i>Malanta</i>
10	<i>Pittanta</i>	<i>Malanta</i>
11	<i>Kaphanta</i>	<i>Malanta</i>
12	<i>Malanta</i>	<i>Pittanta</i>
13	<i>Pittanta</i>	<i>Kaphanta</i>
14	<i>Pittanta</i>	<i>Kaphanta</i>
15	<i>Pittanta</i>	<i>Malanta</i>

Note: *Antiki Lakshana*'s were assessed based on the features exhibited at the end of all Vegas i.e. *Malanta*, *Pittanta*, *Kaphanta* and *Vatanta*. Formed *Mala* of yellowish colour was considered as *Malantha*. At the end of *Vegas* if the colour of the stool was yellowish with slight burning sensation in anal region and having *Visra Gandhi Mala*; it was considered as *Pittanta*. *Mala* of whitish colour with mucous stools were considered as *Kaphanta*. After *Kaphanta* if the stools were frothy along with flatus it was considered as *Vatanta*^[7]

Graph No. 07.

Consistency of stool passed during each *vega* - Bristol stool observed in each group is tabulated as follows

Table No. 09” Showing the Consistency of stool passed during each *vega* - Bristol stool GROUP I ARAGWADHA(*Cassia fistula* Linn.)

Volunter No	Total no of vegas	Type 1	Type 2	Type 3	Type 4	Type 5	Type 6	Type 7
1	16	0	0	0	0	2	0	14
2	5	0	0	0	0	0	4	1
3	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
4	10	0	0	0	0	3	0	7
5	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
6	9	0	0	0	0	0	1	8
7	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
8	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
9	6	0	0	0	0	0	1	5
10	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	9
11	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
12	10	0	0	0	0	0	1	9
13	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
14	5	0	0	0	0	0	1	4
15	16	0	0	0	0	0	1	15

Table no. 10: GROUP II – MESHASHRUNGI(*Gymnema sylvestre*R.Br.).

Volunter No	Total No of Vegas	Type 1	Type 2	Type 3	Type 4	Type 5	Type 6	Type 7
1	26	0	0	0	0	0	1	25
2	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
3	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
4	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
5	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	7
6	10	0	0	0	0	0	1	9
7	15	0	0	0	0	0	1	14
8	20	0	0	0	0	1	2	17
9	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	12
10	22	0	0	0	0	0	2	20
11	21	0	0	0	0	0	0	21
12	9	0	0	0	0	0	1	8
13	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	7
14	16	0	0	0	0	0	1	15
15	10	0	0	0	0	0	1	9

Note : Consistency of stools observed during *Virechana* was assessed based on Bristol stool scale.

Table no. 11: Showing Number of *vegas*.

Variables	Group	N	Mean	SD	Mann-Whitney U test value	p-value	Remarks
No of Vegas	Group 1	15	9.067	4.906	75.5	0.127	Not Significant
	Group 2	15	12.667	6.945			

Graph No. 08.

Table no. 12: Showing Latency periods in minutes.

Variables	Group	N	Mean	SD	Unpaired t-test test value	p-value	Remarks
Latency periods in minutes*	Group 1	15	229.333	50.599	1.780	0.086	Not Significant
	Group 2	15	271.4	76.253			

Graph No. 09.

Table no. 13: Showing the Duration of *Virechana*.

Variables	Group	N	Mean	SD	Unpaired t-test test value	p-value	Remarks
Duration of <i>Virechana</i> *	Group 1	15	152.667	57.721	0.441	0.662	Not Significant
	Group 2	15	161.667	53.886			

Graph No. 10.

Table no. 14: Showing total no of vegas Bristol stool.

Variables	Group	N	Mean	SD	Mann-Whitney U test value	p-value	Remarks
total no of vegas Bristol stool	Group 1	15	8	3.723	64.5	0.047	Significant
	Group 2	15	12.667	6.945			

Graph No. 11.

Total no. 15: Showing Type 5 Bristol stool.

Variables	Group	N	Mean	SD	Mann-Whitney U test value	p-value	Remarks
Type 5 Bristol stool	Group 1	15	0.333	0.9	121	0.524	Not Significant
	Group 2	15	0.067	0.258			

Graph No. 12.**Table no: 16 showing Type 6 Bristol stool.**

Variables	Group	N	Mean	SD	Mann-Whitney U test value	p-value	Remarks
Type 6 Bristol stool	Group 1	15	0.6	1.056	96.5	0.472	Not Significant
	Group 2	15	0.667	0.724			

Graph No. 13.

Table no. 17: Showing Type 7 Bristol stool.

Variables	Group	N	Mean	SD	Unpaired t-test test value	p-value	Remarks
Type 7 Bristol stool*	Group 1	15	7.067	3.615	2.545	0.017	Significant
	Group 2	15	11.933	6.464			

Graph No. 14.

DISCUSSION

- In the literature review it is found that *Aragwadha*(*Cassia fistula* Linn.) *phala majja* is *Madhura Shita* and *Madhura* whereas *Meshashrungi phala* (*Gymnema sylvestre*R.Br.) is *Tikta* , *Ushna* and *Katu*. In the study it is observed that it acts as *Sramsana*, expelling both *Pakwa* and *Apakwa Koshthagata Maladi*. The *ushna virya* and *Katu vipaka* and anthraquinone fistulic acid present in the fruit is responsible for purgation. The total number of *Vegas* and *Dravata* of the stool was more in the volunteers of Group II compared with Group I. Whereas other parameters were almost similar in both the groups. The *Ushna virya* and *Katu vipaka* of *Meshashrungi phala* (*Gymnema sylvestre*R.Br.) must have contributed for the more number of *Vegas* and liquid stools. Both the *Dravyas Aragwadha*(*Cassia fistula* Linn.) and *Meshashrungi*(*Gymnema sylvestre*R.Br.) exhibited same *Sramsana* property in context with Total number of *Vegas*, latency period, duration of *Virechana* and *Antiki Lakshana* indicating both are having equal action so Hypotheses 1 is rejected and Hypotheses 0 is accepted. Hence *Meshashrungi phala* can be used for *Sramsana karma* in place of *Aragwadha*(*Cassia fistula* Linn.) *phala majja*.

CONCLUSION

As per classics of Ayurveda, the *Aragwadha phalamajja* is the *Shreshtha Dravya* for *Sramsana karma* but as in Bhavaprakasha nighantu and Kayadeva nighantu mentioned the *Sramsana karma* for *Meshashrunji phala*, the present study confirms the same clinically. Both *Meshashrunji phala* and *Aragwadha phala majja* act as *Sramsana* so *Meshashrunji phala* can be used in place of *Aragwadha phala majja* for *Sramsanakarma*.

SCOPE OF FUTURE STUDY

The *Meshashrunji phala* is easily available and preparation is easy compared to *Aragwadha phala majja*, so it can be tried in more number of volunteers to analyze *Sramsana* property.

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